

Wave Voxel Synthesis

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ABSTRACT

We present research in sound synthesis techniques employing lookup tables higher than two dimensions. Higher dimensional wavetables have not yet been explored to their fullest potential due to historical resource restrictions, particularly memory. This paper presents a technique for sound synthesis by means of three-variable functions as an extension to existing multidimensional table lookup synthesis techniques.

1. INTRODUCTION

Table lookup techniques are computationally efficient methods for oscillators employed in many sound synthesis applications, including wavetable synthesis, vector synthesis, wave stacking, wave terrain synthesis, scanned synthesis, and many others [1–3]. These techniques employ table indexing operations in one- and two-dimensional spaces.

Our proposed method extends current table-lookup sound synthesis techniques, particularly wave terrain synthesis, with three-variable functions. We introduce the term *wave voxel* to denote three-dimensional lookup tables for sound synthesis.

2. AN OVERVIEW OF 1D AND 2D WAVETABLES

A wavetable of D dimensions consists of precomputed amplitude values stored in a D -dimensional array. An indexing operation takes D indices and retrieves the desired value stored at that particular location of the array.

2.1 1D wavetable

A 1D wavetable is a length N lookup table with sampled amplitude values for one cycle of an arbitrary wave. It is visually represented in two axes, where x is a time axis representing index number from 0 to $N - 1$ and the y axis denotes amplitude. Algorithm 1 writes (one period of) a single sine wave into a wavetable, as in Figure 1.

Algorithm 1

```
for  $i = 0, i < N, i++$  do  
   $table[i] = \sin(2\pi(i/N))$ 
```

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Figure 1. Wavetable of size N .

Indexing a 1D wavetable selects a point on the x axis. As a wavetable contains one cycle of a wave, indexing in this instance is essentially a continuous modular arithmetic phase increment looping through the wavetable.

Algorithm 2

```
phase = 0  
increment = (frequency / samplerate) × tablesizesize  
while true do  
  phase = phase + increment  
  while (phase ≥ tablesizesize) do  
    phase = phase - tablesizesize  
  output = table.interpolate(phase)
```

Algorithm 2 generates incremental phase with the appropriate increment values based on desired frequency, table size N , and sampling rate [4, 5]. Frequency should be between 0 and the nyquist frequency. In general the resulting phase values are floating point numbers, hence the need for some sort of interpolated read from the table (even if just truncating phase to an integer).

Dannenberg demonstrated that the table size required to achieve a given signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) is highly dependent on interpolation method employed [5]. The noise comes from quantization errors both in time and amplitude. A large enough table size would yield a high SNR even without interpolation. Interpolation improves SNR, thus allowing for smaller table sizes, although computation cost will increase. Truncation could produce results that err at most by almost an entire sample, while rounding could produce results that err at most by half a sample. Linear interpolation approximates a waveform curve better, thus producing a lower error, while higher order interpolation methods such as cubic and Catmull-Rom produce even lower error [4].

2.2 2D Wavetable (Wave Terrain)

An extension to the wavetable was formally introduced by Mitsuhashi in [6]. This technique is also known as “wave terrain synthesis,” named after Gold’s use of the term [7, 8]. Wave terrains are generally illustrated as a three-dimensional surface where the Z axis (height) represents amplitude as a function of 2D location X and Y [1], as in Figure 3. Terrains can also be visualized in a two dimensional plot, with color at a pixel location representing the amplitude value at that location, as in Figure 2. Both axes (X and Y) are used for indexing operations in wave terrain synthesis. The path of an indexing operation in a wave terrain is called an *orbit* [9].

This technique of using multidimensional surfaces, introduced by Mitsuhashi, was originally intended for hardware implementation as an alternative for Chowning’s method of FM synthesis [6, 10, 11]. However, it was in 1978 that Gold, a member of the League of Automatic Music Composers, first used the term *wave terrain* to describe a two dimensional map implemented in his instrument, *A Terrain Reader* [7, 8]. In 1986, Borgonovo and Haus implemented a software version of Mitsuhashi’s two-variable technique [10].

Mitsuhashi proposes restrictions for the functions that can be used for terrain generation. He recommended that terrains be continuous in the area of definition and on its boundaries [6, 9]. While Mitsuhashi’s, Borgonovo’s, and Gold’s implementation focused on trigonometric polynomials for terrain generation, latter researches explored other means. Di Scipio experimented with functional iterations [12], Mikelson uses the Julia set as terrains [13], Overholt fabricated a hardware interface for generation of user defined terrains [14], while Dannenberg and Neuendorffer used real-time video images [15].

To illustrate an example of a wave terrain, we referred to an implementation by Comajuncosas in CSound. The pseudocode shown in algorithm 3 generates an N_x by N_y wave terrain containing one cycle of sine wave in each direction, as implemented in [16] and illustrated in Figure 2.

Algorithm 3

```

for  $y = 0, y < N_y, y + +$  do
   $sin_y = \sin(2\pi(y/N_y))$ 
  for  $x = 0, x < N_x, x + +$  do
     $sin_x = \sin(2\pi(x/N_x))$ 
     $table[x][y] = sin_x \times sin_y$ 

```

Amplitude values from -1 to 1 at each location are mapped to color from black to white. Figure 2 visualizes a wave terrain in two dimensions, using color values to represent amplitude values. The same wave terrain, visualized in three dimensions is illustrated in figure 3.

Just as with terrain definitions, there are many different implementations of orbit trajectories. As an example, equations 1 and 2 shows orbit trajectories as implemented by Mitsuhashi [6] and Borgonovo [9].

$$x = 2f_x t + \phi_x + A \sin(2\pi F_x t + \varphi_x) \quad (1)$$

Figure 2. Wave terrain of size N_x by N_y , using pixel brightness to represent amplitude.

Figure 3. Wave terrain in figure 2 visualized in 3D.

$$y = 2f_y t + \phi_y + B \sin(2\pi F_y t + \varphi_y) \quad (2)$$

In the equations above, t denotes time, f_x, f_y, F_x and F_y are frequencies, A and B are amplitudes, and $\phi_x, \phi_y, \varphi_x$, and φ_y are initial phases. These equations can be broken down into two terms: the first, $2ft + \phi$, describes linearity (starting at a given point on the plane and moving in a straight line over time), while the second, $A \sin(2\pi Ft + \varphi)$, describes the nonlinear portion of the equation (Lissajous curves). 2D table indexing, as with 1D, should be wrapped (modulo the table size) so that orbits can go past the boundaries of the terrain. Time-varying values for any one or combinations of variables generate time-varying waveforms.

Wave terrains are by no means restricted to only direct synthesis for sound generation. Other applications have seen the use of wave terrains as a two dimensional surface for dynamic nonlinear distortion or waveshaping, as a control method for multichannel panning, and even as a basis for generative scored compositions [17].

3. 3D WAVETABLE (WAVE VOXEL)

Borgonovo mentioned a higher dimensional approach to wave terrain synthesis [9] but did not implement it at the time due to computational expense. A higher dimensional implementation of wave terrains was implemented by Mikelson in [18]. Mikelson named his implementation *Terrain Mapping Synthesis*, which was written in CSound. His instrument, *Deep Space Growl*, uses a terrain based on a four dimensional polygonal modeling of a torus with spiral orbits in three dimensions.

In this section, we present our approach towards a technique for sound synthesis using three dimensional waveta-

bles. We propose the term *wave voxel*¹ to denote a three dimensional wavetable, and name this technique *wave voxel synthesis*. Our current version is a real-time implementation written in C++ using the openFrameworks² open source toolkit.

Voxel models are widely used in computer graphics for volumetric imaging such as in visualizing scientific data (simulation of smoke), medical applications (MRI, ultrasound), and in video games. A single voxel represents a value on a regular grid in three-dimensional space. A regular grid of N_x by N_y by N_z voxels is called a *voxel stack*, and a voxel stack contains $N_x \times N_y \times N_z$ individual voxels, each with its own value represented by a color or in some instances by opacity [19]. Wave voxels are extensions of wave terrains just as wave terrains are extensions of wavetables. Figure 4 illustrates a $12 \times 12 \times 12$ voxel stack; note that for sound synthesis applications, such small tables generate signals with low SNR.

Figure 4. Stack of wave voxels of size N_x by N_y by N_z . [$N_x = N_y = N_z = 12$]

3.1 Voxel stack

For illustrative purposes, we used cosine waves at each axis in the voxel stack shown in figure 4.³

A stack of wave voxel of size N_x by N_y by N_z , storing amplitude values for a single cycle of a cosine wave as illustrated in figure 4 was generated using the pseudocode shown in algorithm 4.

A three dimensional wavetable can be viewed as layers of wave terrains, stacked on top of one another. Figure 5 illustrates three slices along the Z axis at locations 0, $N_z/2$ and N_z-1 .

¹ “Voxel” is a portmanteau of “volume” and “pixel.”

² <http://www.openframeworks.cc/>

³ As sine waves begins at amplitude 0.0, each voxel at all six faces of the stack will store the same amplitude value of 0.0. Value of 0.0 would be graphically represented by the same gray hue, not very interesting to visualize.

Algorithm 4

```

for  $z = 0, z < N_z, z ++$  do
   $cosz = \cos(2\pi(z/N_z))$ 
  for  $y = 0, y < N_y, y ++$  do
     $cosy = \cos(2\pi(y/N_y))$ 
    for  $x = 0, x < N_x, x ++$  do
       $cosx = \cos(2\pi(x/N_x))$ 
       $table[x][y][z] = cosx \times cosy \times cosz$ 

```

Figure 5. Slices along the Z axis of a $12 \times 12 \times 12$ voxel stack. [Left to right] $table[x][y][0]$, $table[x][y][N_z/2]$ and $table[x][y][N_z - 1]$

3.2 Indexing 3D wavetables

In our current implementation, our approach for three dimensional indexing is shown in equations 3, 4 and 5, which is largely based on equations 1 and 2. We’ve implemented orbits of finite length. Orbit length (I) is the length of the longest axis in the voxel stack (N_x, N_y or N_z).

$$x = 2f_x(i/I) + \phi_x + \mu_x A \sin(2\pi F_x(i/I) + \varphi_x) \quad (3)$$

$$y = 2f_y(i/I) + \phi_y + \mu_y B \sin(2\pi F_y(i/I) + \varphi_y) \quad (4)$$

$$z = 2f_z(i/I) + \phi_z + \mu_z C \sin(2\pi F_z(i/I) + \varphi_z) \quad (5)$$

As in equations 1 and 2, the variables f_x, f_y, f_z, F_x, F_y and F_z denote frequencies, $A, B,$ and C denote amplitude, and $\phi_x, \phi_y, \phi_z, \varphi_x, \varphi_y,$ and φ_z are initial phases. I represents length of orbit, while i is the index or position along an orbit where $0 \leq i < I$.

The variables μ_x, μ_y and μ_z are amplitude envelopes. In our current version, it adds the option to have a constant (equation 6), incremental (equation 7) or triangularly windowed amplitude (equation 8).

$$const(i) = 1.0 \quad (6)$$

$$incr(i) = i/I \quad (7)$$

$$tri(i) = 1.0 - |2i - (I - 1)| \quad (8)$$

With equations 3, 4, and 5, an orbit now inhabits three dimensional space. We’ve implemented three dimensional transformations to maximize control and the capability to generate a variety of waveforms using the same orbit definition. Orbit transformations would also be possible for two dimensional orbits in wave terrain synthesis, although it would be rather restricted compared to transformations in three dimensions.

3.3 Orbit transformations

We apply the standard transformation matrices commonly used in computer graphics [19] to modulate orbits such as those defined above. This changes the spectral characteristics of a signal using a relatively small number of control parameters (particularly with rotation and shearing transformations).

3.3.1 Scale

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} s_x & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & s_y & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & s_z \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

Equation 9 shows the scaling matrix implemented where s_x , s_y and s_z are the scaling factor on x, y and z axis respectively.

3.3.2 Translate

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' \\ y' \\ z' \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & a_x \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & a_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & a_z \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x \\ y \\ z \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

Equation 10 shows translation matrix used to enable orbit translation along x, y and/or z axis where a_x , a_y and a_z are translation amount (in voxels) on x, y and z axis respectively. a_x , a_y and a_z are values denoting offset along a particular axis.

3.3.3 Rotate

$$R_x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos(\alpha) & -\sin(\alpha) \\ 0 & \sin(\alpha) & \cos(\alpha) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_y = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\beta) & 0 & \sin(\beta) \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin(\beta) & 0 & \cos(\beta) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$R_z = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\gamma) & -\sin(\gamma) & 0 \\ \sin(\gamma) & \cos(\gamma) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' & y' & z' \end{bmatrix} = R_x R_y R_z \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

For rotations along x, y, and z axes, we've implemented rotation matrices as shown in equation 11 where α , β and γ are rotation angles when rotating on x, y or z axis respectively. Sign of the value for rotation angle determines direction of rotation.

3.3.4 Shear

$$H_x = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \tan(a) & 1 & 0 \\ \tan(b) & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$H_y = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tan(c) & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & \tan(d) & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$H_z = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \tan(e) \\ 0 & 1 & \tan(f) \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} x' & y' & z' \end{bmatrix} = H_x H_y H_z \begin{bmatrix} x & y & z \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

In a two dimensional plane, a set of vectors could be sheared along the x axis, in which case its y values remains the same after applying transformation. Conversely, shearing is also possible along the y axis in which case its x values are retained after a transformation. Viewing from the z axis in a three dimensional space, we are essentially looking at a two dimensional plane where x axis is the abscissa and y axis the ordinate. Looking at it this way, shearing in a three dimensional space when viewed from the z axis is similar to shearing in two dimensions. Similarly, when viewed along y axis, shearing is possible along x and z axes while viewing from the x axis enables shearing along y and z axes.

Equation 12 shows shearing matrices used, where a and b are shearing degrees on y and z axis respectively when viewed from x axis, c and d are shearing degrees on x and z axis respectively when viewed from y axis and e and f are shearing degrees on x and y axis respectively when viewed from z axis.

As before, the variables a, b, c, d, e and f are angles in degrees and sign of the value for shearing angle determines shearing direction.

3.4 Orbit's origin and modulus

An orbit's trajectory starts at the origin, which is defined to be the center point of a voxel stack at coordinate (0, 0, 0). Modulus for orbits are set to be the size of voxel stack's length, width and height for orbits to wrap around if it exceeds the size of a voxel stack.

As an example, in a voxel stack with 512 voxels on its length, height and width (cube), a trajectory of length 512 traversing in a straight line parallel to the x axis will start at the origin, continues on until it reaches the boundary of the voxel stack at orbit length 256, wraps around to the other end of the axis, continues towards the origin and stops one voxel shy from the origin at orbit length 512. Applying translation on x axis for 256 or -256 voxels would move the orbit so that the trajectory starts at one boundary and ends at the opposite boundary. Figure 6 illustrates this example.

Figure 6. [A] Orbit's start and end point by default. [B] Orbit's start and end point, translated by $-N_x/2$ on x axis.

3.5 Examples of orbits and its resulting waveform

In this section, we present a selection of waveforms generated by specific orbit trajectories. Voxel stack used to generate the waveforms presented in this section are as illustrated in figure 4, but with sine waves instead. Size of voxel stack and orbit length are 512.

For each example presented in this section, both time and frequency domain representations of the waveforms are illustrated, accompanied with orbit trajectory plots (Figure

8) and a table listing values used for each variables (Table 1).

Figure 7. Time and frequency domain representations of a sine wave. [Top] 1st harmonic, [Bottom] 2nd harmonic.

Figure 7 illustrates both time and frequency domain plots as it appears in our current software implementation. The larger portion on the left illustrates time domain representation of the waveform, while the smaller portion on the right illustrates its harmonic contents.

Figure 8. Orbit viewed from x, y and z viewpoints.

Table 1. Values for orbit shown in figure 8.

linear frequency (f_x, f_y, f_z)	linear phase (ϕ_x, ϕ_y, ϕ_z)	amplitude (A, B, C)	amp. envelope (μ_x, μ_y, μ_z)	frequency (F_x, F_y, F_z)	phase ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$)
1, 0, 0	0, 0.5, -0.5	0, 0, 0	a, a, a	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0
scale (s_x, s_y, s_z)	translate (a_x, a_y, a_z)	rotate (α, β, γ)	shear x (a, b)	shear y (c, d)	shear z (e, f)
1, 1, 1	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	0, 0	0, 0	0, 0

Figure 8 illustrates trajectory of orbit viewed from x, y and z axis viewpoints. The color coded crosshairs are axis reference, where colors red, green and blue represents x, y and z axis respectively.

Waveform shown in figure 7 [Top] were generated by trajectory shown in figure 8, using values listed in table 1. For the waveform shown in figure 7 [Bottom], x axis linear frequency (f_x) is set to 2.

Linear phases (ϕ_x, ϕ_y and ϕ_z) and phases (φ_x, φ_y and φ_z) are normalized to 1.0. Both rotation angles (α, β and γ), and shearing angles (a, b, c, d, e and f) are in degrees, while translation values (a_x, a_y and a_z) are by number of voxels.

Amplitude envelope variables (μ_x, μ_y and μ_z) are listed as characters 'a', 'b' or 'c' representing either a constant value (equation 6), a linear ramp (equation 7) or a triangular window (equation 8) respectively.

Figure 9. Orbit/Waveform example01

Table 2. Values for orbit/waveform shown in figure 9.

linear frequency (f_x, f_y, f_z)	linear phase (ϕ_x, ϕ_y, ϕ_z)	amplitude (A, B, C)	amp. envelope (μ_x, μ_y, μ_z)	frequency (F_x, F_y, F_z)	phase ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$)
0, 0, 1	0, 0, 0	0.65, 0.65, 0	a, a, a	1, 1, 0	0, 0.25, 0
scale (s_x, s_y, s_z)	translate (a_x, a_y, a_z)	rotate (α, β, γ)	shear x (a, b)	shear y (c, d)	shear z (e, f)
1, 1, 1	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	0, 0	0, 0	0, 0

Figure 10. Waveform example01 (Figure 9) [Left] frequency sweep (50hz to 1khz), [Right] harmonic contents at 1hz.

Figure 11. Orbit/Waveform example02

Table 3. Values for orbit/waveform shown in figure 11.

linear frequency (f_x, f_y, f_z)	linear phase (ϕ_x, ϕ_y, ϕ_z)	amplitude (A, B, C)	amp. envelope (μ_x, μ_y, μ_z)	frequency (F_x, F_y, F_z)	phase ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$)
0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	0.75, 0.75, 1	a, a, a	4, 3, 1	0, 0, 0
scale (s_x, s_y, s_z)	translate (a_x, a_y, a_z)	rotate (α, β, γ)	shear x (a, b)	shear y (c, d)	shear z (e, f)
1, 1, 1	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	0, 0	0, 0	0, 0

Figure 12. Waveform example02 (Figure 11) [Left] frequency sweep (50hz to 1khz), [Right] harmonic contents at 1hz.

Figure 13. Orbit/Waveform example03

Table 4. Values for orbit/waveform shown in figure 13.

linear frequency (f_x, f_y, f_z)	linear phase (ϕ_x, ϕ_y, ϕ_z)	amplitude (A, B, C)	amp. envelope (μ_x, μ_y, μ_z)	frequency (F_x, F_y, F_z)	phase ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$)
0, 0, 1	0, 0, 0	1, 1, 0	b, b, a	5, 5, 0	0.25, 0, 0
scale (s_x, s_y, s_z)	translate (a_x, a_y, a_z)	rotate (α, β, γ)	shear x (a, b)	shear y (c, d)	shear z (e, f)
1, 1, 1	0, 0, 256	0, 0, 0	0, 0	0, 0	0, 0

Figure 14. Waveform example03 (Figure 13) [Left] frequency sweep (50hz to 1khz), [Right] harmonic contents at 1hz.

Figure 15. Orbit/Waveform example04

Table 5. Values for orbit/waveform shown in figure 15.

linear frequency (f_x, f_y, f_z)	linear phase (ϕ_x, ϕ_y, ϕ_z)	amplitude (A, B, C)	amp. envelope (μ_x, μ_y, μ_z)	frequency (F_x, F_y, F_z)	phase ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$)
5, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	0, 1, 1	a, c, c	0, 6, 6	0, 0.25, 0
scale (s_x, s_y, s_z)	translate (a_x, a_y, a_z)	rotate (α, β, γ)	shear x (a, b)	shear y (c, d)	shear z (e, f)
1, 1, 1	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	0, 0	0, 0	0, 0

Figure 16. Waveform example04 (Figure 15) [Left] frequency sweep (50hz to 1khz), [Right] harmonic contents at 1hz.

Figure 17. Orbit/Waveform example05

Table 6. Values for orbit/waveform shown in figure 17.

linear frequency (f_x, f_y, f_z)	linear phase (ϕ_x, ϕ_y, ϕ_z)	amplitude (A, B, C)	amp. envelope (μ_x, μ_y, μ_z)	frequency (F_x, F_y, F_z)	phase ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$)
10, 10, 0	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 1	a, a, a	0, 0, 1	0, 0, 0
scale (s_x, s_y, s_z)	translate (a_x, a_y, a_z)	rotate (α, β, γ)	shear x (a, b)	shear y (c, d)	shear z (e, f)
1, 1, 1	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	45, 0	0, 0	0, 0

Figure 18. Waveform example05 (Figure 17) [Left] frequency sweep (50hz to 1khz), [Right] harmonic contents at 1hz.

Figure 19. Orbit/Waveform example06

Table 7. Values for orbit/waveform shown in figure 19.

linear frequency (f_x, f_y, f_z)	linear phase (ϕ_x, ϕ_y, ϕ_z)	amplitude (A, B, C)	amp. envelope (μ_x, μ_y, μ_z)	frequency (F_x, F_y, F_z)	phase ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$)
0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	1, 1, 1	a, a, a	2, 1, 3	0, 0, 0
scale (s_x, s_y, s_z)	translate (a_x, a_y, a_z)	rotate (α, β, γ)	shear x (a, b)	shear y (c, d)	shear z (e, f)
1.5, 1, 1.75	0, 0, 0	45, 0, 0	0, 0	30, 0	45, 0

Figure 20. Waveform example06 (Figure 19) [Left] frequency sweep (50hz to 1khz), [Right] harmonic contents at 1hz.

Figure 21. Orbit/Waveform example07

Table 8. Values for orbit/waveform shown in figure 21.

linear frequency (f_x, f_y, f_z)	linear phase (ϕ_x, ϕ_y, ϕ_z)	amplitude (A, B, C)	amp. envelope (μ_x, μ_y, μ_z)	frequency (F_x, F_y, F_z)	phase ($\varphi_x, \varphi_y, \varphi_z$)
1, 1, 1	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0	a, a, a	0, 0, 0	0, 0, 0
scale (s_x, s_y, s_z)	translate (a_x, a_y, a_z)	rotate (α, β, γ)	shear x (a, b)	shear y (c, d)	shear z (e, f)
5, 2, 3	0, 0, 0	0, 15, 0	0, 33	0, 0	89, 0

Figure 22. Waveform example07 (Figure 21) [Left] frequency sweep (50hz to 1khz), [Right] harmonic contents at 1hz.

At the moment we have only explored time-invariant orbits with waveforms generated using sine waves that is isomorphic in x, y and z axes to generate voxel stack content. Using pure tones allows us to better understand harmonic contents of a waveform generated by a particular orbit. To fully maximize the potential of this technique, a voxel model should store data that differs at each axis with dynamic orbits trajectories.

Sound files for each example presented in this section are available for streaming online.⁴

3.6 Aliasing

As visually apparent in the frequency sweep plots shown in the previous section, we’ve ignored aliasing issues in our current software implementation.

One solution for this issue would be to increase its sampling rate. As an alternative, another approach would be to implement multiple sub-wavetables [20]. For example, suppose the desired frequency range is from 20hz to 22.05khz. This range corresponds to roughly ten octaves from the lowest frequency (20hz to 20.48khz).

In this instance, we could construct ten sub-wavetables, one for each octave. Harmonic contents of each sub-wave table are reduced as the octave gets higher. Ultimately, the sub-wavetable for the highest octave contains only a single period of sine tone. Based on the desired output frequency, a specific sub-wavetable is chosen out of the ten created. This approach guarantees a bandlimited output.

3.7 Resizing of orbit for synthesis

In order to generate audio signals with an acceptable SNR, wavetables are generally implemented in powers of two with 2048 or 4096 samples in size. As in wave terrain synthesis, orbit length correlates to wavetable length. In our current implementation, length of orbit is the same length as voxel stack size ($N=512$), which is insufficient to produce signals with an acceptable SNR. To construct a larger

⁴ <https://soundcloud.com/anisharon/sets/smc2015-wave-voxel-synthesis>

wavetable, we resized the orbit using catmull-rom spline interpolation [19].

4. CONCLUSIONS & FUTURE WORK

We introduced the term wave voxel to denote a three dimensional lookup table for sound synthesis. We proposed a new method for sound synthesis by means of three-variable functions as an extension to existing multidimensional table lookup synthesis techniques, presented a method for visualizing three dimensional lookup tables using volumetric representations, and demonstrated a table indexing method for use with three dimensional wavetables based on previous research in multidimensional scanning by Mitsuhashi and Borgonovo/Haus.

A study on comparison with other synthesis techniques is ongoing at the time of writing. Part of our ongoing work is exploring other means in creating orbit trajectories. Besides implementing other types of affine transformations, we are interested in experimenting with time-varying orbits, dynamic modulation of orbits using transformations, orbit trajectories based on summation of spherical curves [21], three dimensional knight’s tour [22] and dynamic vector fields.

We are also interested in exploring the possibility of using dynamic voxel stack contents, for instance by traversing a voxel stack through samples of recorded audio, where each axis would store different snippets of recordings. In this instance, a voxel stack can be thought of as a three dimensional rectangular granulation window. We will also look into volumetric scene reconstruction from multiple cameras [23] as a method for generating dynamic voxel stack contents. Also pertinent to our research are interfacing and control methods to effectively control our proposed technique for use as an instrument in live setups.

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